

Obstacles of the Application of Total Quality Management in the Directorate of Youth and Sports from the Point of View of Workers and Employees of the Souk Ahras Directorate of Youth and Sports.

Imen Ghalmi

Laboratory of Sports and High Level Training , University Mohamed Cherif Mesadia
Souk Ahras, Algeria.

i.ghalmi@univ-soukahras.dz

ARTICLE INFORMATION	ABSTRACT
<p>ORIGINAL RESEARCH PAPER RECEIVED : 04/07/2022 ACCEPTED : 08/11/2022 PUBLISHED: 01/12/2022</p>	<p>Through this study, we tried to become familiar with the issue of obstacles to the application of total quality management in the Directorate of Youth and Sports from the point of view of Souk Ahras. The research sample consisted of 27 male and female workers and employees of the Directorate of Youth and Sports, Souk Ahras. We used the descriptive analytical method based on the questionnaire as a tool for the study. The most important results reached through this study were the existence of organizational obstacles, administrative obstacles, human obstacles, and financial obstacles that prevent the application of total quality management in the Directorate of Youth and Sports in Souk Ahras.</p>
<p>KEYWORDS : Management Total quality Youth and sports Directorate</p>	
<p>Auteur correspondant : Imen Ghalmi, e-mail: i.ghalmi@univ-soukahras.dz</p>	

1. Introduction

The topic of the application of total quality management has received a large share of the application. This is due to its success in various institutions around the world because total quality management is one of the methods through which it is possible to respond to the challenges facing institutions and achieve the required transformation. It also represents one of the most important policies aimed at developing performance and seeking continuous improvement; achieving the best inputs, processes, and outputs; providing the best services to the beneficiaries, and entering the competition arena.

The application of total quality management in the Directorate of Youth and Sports has become an urgent requirement in order to interact and deal efficiently with the variables of an era characterized by the acceleration of knowledge and technology. In which the fever of conflict and competition between individuals, groups, and institutions is increasing.

As Omar Wasfi Aqili has pointed out: “Quality means the production of the institution or the provision of a service with a high level of distinguished quality, through which it is able to fulfill the needs and desires of its customers, in a manner consistent with their expectations, and to achieve their satisfaction and happiness. This is done through pre-established standards for the production of the commodity or the provision of the service and finding the characteristic of excellence in it.” (Aqili, 2001, p. 17)

The introduction of quality in the Directorate of Youth and Sports enables us to achieve quality performance, which is a tool for development and progress and its integration in knowledge, skills, and emotions, and then fulfill the needs of the community of specialized cadres capable of competition.

The application of total quality management is very important in order to advance and develop at high levels of performance and quality. Also, to improve administrative service efficiency.

The Directorate of Youth and Sports is defined as “an executive body affiliated to the sector of the Ministry of Youth and Sports, where it is supervised by an executive director who is delegated by the Wali and which ensures the serious work of the internal and external administration. It is a body that works to promote the associative movements of youth and sports, as well as their structures and organization, and the preparation of targeted programs and the generalization of sports, especially in the educational and

training environment and framework, as well as preparing plans for the development of sports for the state in coordination with all the structures and bodies concerned.” (Directorate of Youth and Sports Souk Ahras)

This topic has been successful in the application of youth and sports directorates, as many of the latter have adopted the philosophy of total quality management and applied it with the aim of working on continuous improvement in performance as well as raising the efficiency of workers to ensure a good return for them.

Undoubtedly, the Directorate of Youth and Sports faces problems and challenges in terms of the level of application of total quality management and the appropriateness of its programs for workers and administrators. It also faces huge challenges related to its ability to develop human and material resources and the great changes taking place in our contemporary world to ensure the skills and knowledge formed by the workers of the Directorate of Youth and Sports and faces other challenges due to the rapid technological development and global systems.

As a result of the growing interest globally and locally in applying total quality management in the directorates of youth and sports, and in line with modern trends in administrative concepts represented by the entrance of total quality management, we can face the rapid changes and challenges in various fields, and find possible solutions to problems.

The introduction of comprehensive quality in the Directorate of Youth and Sports achieves the quality of performance, which is the tool for development and progress and leads to meeting the needs of the community of specialized cadres capable of competition.

Given the importance of this topic and its many aspects, the problem of the current study is based on asking the following main question:

- What are the obstacles to the application of total quality management in the Directorate of Youth and Sports from the point of view of the workers and employees of the Directorate of Youth and Sports, Souk Ahras?

2. Literary Review

4-1- The First Study Was by Munir bin Muhamad Said bin Muhamad Qutb in 2008. In 2008, the researcher Muhammad conducted a study entitled “The Possibility of Applying the Foundations of Total Quality in the Management and Organization of Sports Activity in the General Education Stages in the Schools of the Holy Capital (Saudi Arabia). It is a study presented to complete the requirements for obtaining a master's degree in educational administration and planning at Umm Al-Qura University.

The following results were obtained: -The degree of importance of applying total quality management in managing and organizing sports activity in general education stages from the point of view of physical education supervisors and teachers was high. -The degree of challenges facing teachers in applying total quality management to managing and organizing sports activity from the point of view of physical education supervisors and teachers was medium. -There is a strong positive correlation between each requirement and all requirements for applying the foundations of total quality in the management and organization of sports activity from the point of view of physical education supervisors and teachers in the Saudi Arabia.

4-2 The Second Study Was by Researcher Al-Abed Hawari in 2014-2015. The researcher Al-Abed Hawari conducted a study in 2014-2015 entitled “Total Quality Management as an Entry to Improving the Performance of Human Resources in the Local Administration in Adrar” with a graduation thesis to obtain a master’s degree in political science at the University of Mohamed Khider – Biskra.

Results: -Most of the employees in the local administration have full knowledge of the concepts related to total quality management. -Most employees are aware of the benefits resulting from the application of total quality management, the most important of which is that it leads to an interest in training, continuing education, and collective cooperation.

4-3 The Third Study was by Aaqaq Khadidja 2018/2019. In 2018/2019, the researcher conducted a study under the title “Obstacles to the Application of Total Quality Management in Higher Educational Institutions” with a memorandum presented to complete the requirements for a master’s degree in the Faculty of Economic, Commercial, and Management Sciences at the University of Mohamed Boudiaf in M’sila.

The results of this study -There are organizational obstacles at an acceptable level with statistical significance that prevent the application of total quality management in higher education institutions from the point of view of the

faculty members at the Faculty of Economics, M'sila University. -There are administrative obstacles at an acceptable level with statistical significance that prevent the application of total quality management in higher education institutions from the point of view of the faculty members at the Faculty of Economics, M'sila University. -There are human obstacles at an acceptable level with statistical significance that prevent the application of total quality management in higher education institutions from the point of view of the faculty members at the Faculty of Economics, M'sila University. -There are financial obstacles at an acceptable level with statistical significance that prevent the application of total quality management in higher education institutions from the point of view of the faculty members at the Faculty of Economics, M'sila University. -There are material obstacles at an acceptable level with statistical significance that prevent the application of total quality management in higher education institutions from the point of view of the faculty members at the Faculty of Economics, M'sila University.

4-4 The Fourth Study Was by Researchers Zainab Basu and Noura Mahboub in 2012-2013. In 2012-2013, the two researchers conducted a study entitled “The Impact of Total Quality Management on the Performance of Employees” with a memorandum submitted to complete the requirements for the Bachelor’s degree, Department of Management Sciences, Kasdi Merbah University.

- The results: The results of the study showed that the elements of total quality management (commitment of higher management, continuous improvement, and employee participation) have a high impact on raising the level of performance of workers. Also, it showed that improving worker performance is one of the most important factors for the success of total quality management. The results of the study showed that the level of performance of employees is directly affected by successful quality management.

3. The Methodological Procedures of the Study

5-1- The Method Used in the Study

A descriptive approach is a set of rules and procedures established and designated by research methodology specialists that the researcher uses to reach and reveal the truth, which leads to sound research results (Nasrallah, 2016, page 02). So our study includes the descriptive analytical approach because it is the most appropriate for this study to achieve its goals, as it aims to describe the phenomenon as it is in the field.

5-2- Study Population and Sample

5-2-1- Study Population

It is the study population from which field data is collected. In order for the research to be acceptable and feasible, it is necessary to define the research community that we want to examine and to clarify the standards in order to limit this community. (Ibrahim, 2004, p. 66).

The population of our study consisted of a group of workers and employees of the Directorate of Youth and Sports, Souk Ahras, of both sexes.

5-2-2- Study Sample

It is a subset of the study population that is selected in a certain way, the study is conducted on it, and then those results are used and generalized to the original study population. (Abu Tamer, 2003, p. 53) The sample of our research included workers and employees of the Directorate of Youth and Sports, Souk Ahras, of both sexes, which numbered 27 male and female workers.

6- Data Collection Tools

In our study, we relied mainly on the questionnaire in order to choose the research hypotheses. The questionnaire used in the study consisted of two parts:

- **The first part of the questionnaire:** represents personal data.
- **The second part of the questionnaire:** represents the various dimensions and aspects used in the study.

7- Statistical Methods

This study used the statistical package system SPSS for its eighteenth version, which is the most important and most popular ready-made software package in the field of statistical data processing. This program has many characteristics, including simplicity of use and ease of understanding.

The following statistical techniques were used:

-Iterations, Percentages, K2, Pearson's simple correlation coefficient.

8- Presentation, Interpretation, and Discussion of the Results:

8-1- The First Axis: "obstacles related to the organizational aspect."

8-1-1- Presentation of the Results of the First Axis:

Table (01) results for the first axis

	Calculated k ²	Tabulated k ²	Degree of freedom	Significance level	Statistical significance
The first statement: the inadequacy of the TQM organizational structure in the Directorate of Youth and Sports	12.07	9.49	04	0.05	Statistically significance
The second statement: The powers granted to the administration officials are limited to the performance of their duties.	25.04	9.49	04	0.05	Statistically significance
The Third Statement: The organizational climate is not suitable for the application of total quality management in the Directorate of Youth and Sports in Souk Ahras.	10.59	9.49	04	0.05	Statistically significance
The Fourth Statement: lack of flexibility in carrying out tasks.	9.85	9.49	04	0.05	Statistically significance
The Fifth Statement: Weakness of communication channels between organizational units.	9.85	9.49	04	0.05	Statistically significance
The sixth Statement: The teamwork did not rise to the level qualified in applying TQM in the Directorate of Youth and Sports in Souk Ahras.	2.44	9.49	04	0.05	Statistically not significance
The Seventh Statement: the lack of objective criteria for measuring organizational performance.	12.07	9.49	04	0.05	Statistically significance
The Eighth Statement: the bureaucratic nature prevailing over the organizational climate in the Directorate of Youth and Sports in Souk Ahras.	4.30	9.49	04	0.05	Statistically not significance

8-1-2- Analysis of the Results of the First Axis

Through Table (01), we note for the first statement that the calculated k² value of 12.07 is more than the tabulated k² value of 9.49. This indicates that there is statistical significance in favor of the workers who abide by the impartiality regarding the inappropriateness of the TQM organizational structure in the Directorate of Youth and Sports.

Also, the calculated k² value for the second statement, which is 25.04, is more than the tabulated K² value, which is 9.49. This indicates that there is a statistical significance in favor of workers who agree that the powers granted to management officials are limited to performing their tasks.

As for the third statement, which is represented by the organizational climate that is not suitable for the application of total quality management in the Directorate of Youth and Sports in Souk Ahras, we found that the calculated k² value of 10.59 is more than the tabulated k² value of 9.49. This indicates a statistical significance in favor of workers, those who do not agree that the organizational climate is not appropriate for the application of total quality management in the Directorate of Youth and Sports in Souk Ahras.

We also note that for the fourth statement, which states the lack of flexibility in carrying out the tasks, the calculated K² value of 9.85 is more

than the tabulated K2 value of 9.49. This indicates a statistical significance in favor of workers who agree that they lack flexibility in carrying out tasks.

As for the fifth statement, which revolves around the weakness of communication channels between organizational units, we note that the calculated K2 value of 9.85 is more than the tabulated K2 value of 9.49. This indicates that there is a statistical significance in favor of workers who do not agree with the weakness of communication channels between organizational units.

In the sixth statement, we also concluded that the calculated k2 value of 2.44 is less than the tabulated k2 value of 9.49, which indicates the absence of statistical significance in the workers' answers.

As for the seventh statement, which states the lack of objective criteria for measuring organizational performance, we concluded that the calculated k2 value of 12.07 is more than the tabulated K2 value of 9.49, which indicates that there is a statistical significance in favor of workers who agree with the lack of standards Objective to measure organizational performance.

In the eighth statement, which states that the bureaucratic character prevails over the organizational climate in the Directorate of Youth and Sports in Souk Ahras, we note that the calculated k2 value of 4.30 is less than the tabulated k2 value of 9.49, which indicates the absence of statistical significance in workers' answers.

8-2- The Second Axis: "Obstacles related to the administrative aspect."

8-2-1- Presentation of the Results of the Second Axis:

Table (02) Results for the Second Axis

	Calculated k^2	Tabulated k^2	Degree of freedom	Significance level	Statistical significance
The ninth statement : The higher management's lack of interest in the application of TQM.	6.52	9.49	04	0.05	Statistically not significance
The tenth statement: the administrative levels did not respond to the application of the TQM requirements set by the higher management	16.15	9.49	04	0.05	Statistically significance
The eleventh statement: The inflexibility of administrative processes between the various units	12.07	9.49	04	0.05	Statistically significance
The twelfth statement: the lack of trust between the administrative units in the Directorate of Youth and Sports, Souk Ahras.	2.44	9.49	04	0.05	Statistically not significance
The thirteenth statement: Weak encouragement by the Directorate of Youth and Sports in Souk Ahras to participate in conferences.	5.78	9.49	04	0.05	Statistically not significance
The fourteenth statement: The lack of seminars on the application of TQM principles by the Directorate of Youth and Sports in Souk Ahras.	6.52	9.49	04	0.05	Statistically not significance
The fifteenth statement: There is a high degree of centralization in decision-making in the Directorate of Youth and Sports in Souk Ahras.	18.74	9.49	04	0.05	Statistically significance
The sixteenth statement: The goals are not measurable.	10.96	9.49	04	0.05	Statistically significance

8-2-2- Analysis of the Results of the Second Axis

Through Table (02), the results were as follows:

In ninth statement , we notice that the calculated k^2 value, which is 6.52, is less than the tabulated K^2 value, which is 9.49, which indicates that there is no statistical significance in the workers' answers.

As for the tenth statement, which revolves around the lack of response by the administrative levels to the application of the TQM requirements set by the higher management, we note that the calculated K^2 value of 16.15 is more than the tabulated K^2 value of 9.49, which indicates the existence of statistical significance in favor of workers who do not agree that the administrative levels do not respond to the application of the TQM requirements set by the higher management.

We found in the eleventh statement that the calculated value of k^2 , which is 12.07, is more than the tabulated value of k^2 , which is 9.49. This indicates that there is a statistical significance in favor of workers who do not agree on the inflexibility of administrative processes between the various units.

As for the twelfth statement, which revolves around the lack of confidence between the administrative units in the Directorate of Youth and Sports in Souk Ahras, the calculated k^2 value of 2.44 was less than the

tabulated k2 value of 9.49, which indicates the absence of statistical significance in workers answers.

As for the thirteenth statement, which is about the weakness of encouraging the administration of the Directorate of Youth and Sports in Souk Ahras to participate in conferences, the calculated k2 value of 5.78 was less than the tabulated k2 value of 9.49, which indicates that there is no significance Statistics in workers' answers.

In the fourteenth statement, about the lack of seminars on the application of TQM principles by the Directorate of Youth and Sports in Souk Ahras, the calculated k2 value of 6.52 was less than the tabulated k2 value of 9.49, which indicates the absence of statistical significance in workers answers.

As for the fifteenth statement, which revolves around the presence of a high degree of centralization in decision-making in the Directorate of Youth and Sports in Souk Ahras, the calculated k2 value of 18.74 was more than the tabulated k2 value of 9.49, which indicates a statistical significance in favor of workers who agree that there is a high degree of centralization in decision-making in the Directorate of Youth and Sports in Souk Ahras.

As for the sixteenth statement, which talks about the inability of goals to be measured, the calculated k2 value of 10.96 was more than the tabulated K2 value of 9.49, which indicates the existence of statistical significance in favor of workers who abide by the neutrality regarding the inability of goals to be measured.

8-3- The Third Axis: "obstacles related to the human side."

8-3-1- Presentation of the Results of the Third Axis

Table (03) Results for the Third Axis

	Calculated k^2	Tabulated k^2	Degree of freedom	Significance level	Statistical significance
The Seventeenth Statement: lack of sufficient knowledge of workers on TQM principles.	8.74	9.49	04	0.05	Statistically not significance
The Eighteenth Statement: There are no incentives for workers to implement TQM.	9.85	9.49	04	0.05	Statistically significance
The Nineteenth Statement: Not involving the workers in preparing the strategic planning for the Directorate of Youth and Sports, Souk Ahras.	3.19	9.49	04	0.05	Statistically not significance
The Twentieth Statement: The lack of training courses directed at developing the efficiency of the presence of employees.	8.74	9.49	04	0.05	Statistically not significance
The Twenty-first Statement: Weak workers' interest in the concept of adopting TQM application and considering it unnecessary.	9.85	9.49	04	0.05	Statistically significance
The Twenty-second Statement: The Directorate of Youth and Sports, Souk Ahras, is not interested in spreading the concepts and requirements of TQM among workers.	9.41	9.49	04	0.05	Statistically not significance
The Twenty-third Statement: The lack of experience needed by workers to implement TQM.	14.30	9.49	04	0.05	Statistically significance
The Twenty-fourth Statement: preparing future plans for the application of TQM in the Directorate of Youth and Sports, Souk Ahras.	9.85	9.49	04	0.05	Statistically significance

8-3-2- Analysis of the Results of the Third Axis

Through Table (3), we notice that the seventeenth statement, which states that workers lack sufficient knowledge of TQM principles. The calculated K^2 value of 8.74 is less than the tabulated K^2 value of 9.49, which indicates that there is no significance in the workers' answers.

As for the eighteenth statement, which revolves around the lack of incentives allocated to workers for the application of TQM, the calculated K^2 value of 9.85 is more than the tabulated K^2 value of 9.49. This indicates a statistical significance in favor of workers who agree that there are no incentives dedicated to workers for the application of TQM.

The results of the nineteenth statement, which revolve around the non-involvement of workers in preparing the strategic planning for the Directorate of Youth and Sports in Souk Ahras, the calculated k^2 of 3.19 is less than the tabulated k^2 value of 9.49, which indicates the absence of statistical significance in Workers' answers.

As for the twentieth statement, which is the lack of training courses directed to developing the efficiency of the presence of workers, we note that the calculated k^2 value, which is 8.74, is less than the tabulated k^2 value, which is 9.49, which indicates the absence of statistical significance in the workers' answers.

The results of the twenty-first statement, which revolve around the workers' weak interest in the concept of adopting the TQM application and considering it unnecessary, was the calculated K^2 value of 9.85 more than the tabulated K^2 value of 9.49, which indicates the presence of statistical significance in favor of workers who agree that workers have little interest in the concept of TQM adoption as unnecessary.

As for the twenty-second statement, which is the lack of interest of the Directorate of Youth and Sports in Souk Ahras in disseminating the concepts and requirements of TQM among workers, the calculated k^2 value of 9.41 was less than the tabulated k^2 value of 9.49, which indicates the absence of statistical significance in the worker's answers.

In the twenty-third statement, which states the lack of experience necessary for workers to apply TQM, the calculated K^2 value of 14.30 was more than the tabulated K^2 value of 9.49, which indicates the presence of statistical significance in favor of workers who agree the lack of experience necessary for workers to apply TQM.

As for the twenty-fourth statement, which is preparing future plans for the application of TQM in the Directorate of Youth and Sports in Souk Ahras, we noticed that the calculated k^2 value, which is 9.85, is more than the tabulated k^2 value, which is 9.49, and this indicates that there is a statistical significance in favor of workers who agree to prepare future plans for the TQM application in the Directorate of Youth and Sports in Souk Ahras.

8-4- The Fourth Axis: "Obstacles Related to the Material Aspect."

8-4-1- Presentation of the Results of the Fourth Axis

Table (04) Results for the Fourth Axis

	Calculated k ²	Tabulated k ²	Degree of freedom	Significance level	Statistical significance
The Twenty-fifth Statement: Reliance on the financial appropriations allocated by the Ministry only.	9.85	9.49	04	0.05	Statistically significance
The Twenty-sixth Statement: The absence of financial partners from the private sector.	15.04	9.49	04	0.05	Statistically significance
The Twenty-seventh Statement: Insufficient funding sources to achieve the planned goals.	6.89	9.49	04	0.05	Statistically not significance
The Twenty-eighth Statement: Not allocating additional funds for the adoption of TQM.	9.85	9.49	04	0.05	Statistically significance
The Twenty-ninth Statement: Not allocating sufficient funds to the budget of the Directorate of Youth and Sports, Souk Ahras.	4.67	9.49	04	0.05	Statistically not significance
The Thirtieth Statement: Double coverage of the expenses of the Directorate of Youth and Sports, Souk Ahras.	3.19	9.49	04	0.05	Statistically not significance
The Thirty-first Statement: The lack of sufficient spaces for workers in the Directorate of Youth and Sports, Souk Ahras.	6.52	9.49	04	0.05	Statistically not significance
The Thirty-second Statement: The lack of electronic devices and perhaps networks in the Directorate of Youth and Sports, Souk Ahras	19.85	9.49	04	0.05	Statistically significance

8-4-2- Analysis of the Results of the Fourth Axis

Through Table (04), which includes the results of the third axis, the twenty-fifth statement, which states that rely on the financial appropriations allocated by the Ministry only. We note that the calculated K2 value of 9.85 is more than the tabulated K2 value of 9.49, and this provides evidence for the existence of statistical significance in favor of workers who fully agree to rely on the financial appropriations allocated by the Ministry only.

As for the twenty-sixth statement, about the absence of financial partners from the private sector, the calculated K2 value of 15.04 is more than the tabulated K2 value of 9.49. This indicates a statistical significance in favor of workers who fully agree with the lack of financial partners from the private sector.

The results of the twenty-seventh statement, which revolve around the inadequacy of funding sources to achieve the planned goals, were the calculated K2 value of 6.89 less than the tabulated K2 value of 9.49, which indicates the absence of statistical significance in the workers' answers.

As for the twenty-eighth statement, which states to did not allocate additional funds for the adoption of TQM, the results of the calculated K2 value of 9.85 were more than the tabulated K2 value of 9.49. This indicates

a statistical significance in favor of workers who fully agree not to allocate additional funds for TQM adoption.

In the twenty-ninth statement about not allocating sufficient funds to the budget of the Directorate of Youth and Sports in Souk Ahras, the calculated k^2 value of 4.67 was less than the tabulated k^2 value of 9.49, which indicates the absence of statistical significance in the workers' answers.

As for the thirtieth statement, which revolves around the poor coverage of the expenses of the Directorate of Youth and Sports in Souk Ahras, we note that the calculated k^2 value of 3.19 is less than the tabulated k^2 value of 9.49, which indicates the absence of statistical significance in the workers' answers.

The results of the thirty-first statement, which talks about the lack of sufficient spaces for workers in the Directorate of Youth and Sports, Souk Ahras, the calculated k^2 value of 6.52 is less than the tabulated k^2 value of 9.49, which indicates that there is no statistical significance in the workers' answers.

In the thirty-second statement, which centers on the lack of electronic devices and perhaps networks in the Directorate of Youth and Sports in Souk Ahras, the calculated k^2 value of 19.85 was more than the tabulated k^2 value of 9.49, which indicates a statistical significance in favor of workers who fully agree with the lack of electronic devices and perhaps networks in the Directorate of Youth and Sports in Souk Ahras.

9- Discussing:

- Analysis and Discussion of the Results of the General Hypothesis "Total quality management has administrative, human, organizational, and financial obstacles that prevent its use in the Directorate of Youth and Sports, Souk Ahras." Through the results, we concluded that the hypothesis is validated and is consistent with the study of Aqaq Khadija 2019, but it differs from the rest of the studies.
- Analysis and Discussion of the Results of the First Partial Hypothesis "There are organizational obstacles that prevent the total quality management application in the Directorate of Youth and Sports, Souk Ahras." It is clear from Tables (6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13) that there are obstacles related to the organizational aspect, including the partial hypothesis "there are obstacles related to the organizational aspect" achieved. The results of this study are consistent with the results of the study by Aqaq Khadija 2019, which found that there are obstacles related to the organizational aspect at

M'sila University. We also find that our study is inconsistent with the rest of the other studies.

- Analysis and Discussion of the Results of the Second Partial Hypothesis “There are administrative obstacles that prevent the use of the application of total quality management in the Directorate of Youth and Sports, Souk Ahras.” Through tables (14,15,16,17,18,19,20,21), it is clear that there are administrative obstacles, including this hypothesis is verified. The results of our study agree with the study of Aqaq Khadija 2019, which concluded that there are obstacles related to the administrative aspect of M'sila University. It also agrees with the study of the two students, Zainab Basu and Noura Mahboub (2013), whereby the researchers concluded that there are administrative obstacles that affect the performance of workers in the Oasis Mills-Tougourt. As for the rest of the studies, we found that their results contradict the results of this hypothesis.
- Analysis and Discussion of the Results of the Third Partial Hypothesis “There are human obstacles that prevent the total quality management application in the Directorate of Youth and Sports, Souk Ahras.” It is clear to us through the tables (22,23,24,25,26,27,28,29) that there are obstacles related to the human aspect. Hence, we conclude that this hypothesis is valid. The results of the study of this hypothesis agree with the study of Aqaq Khadija (2019), which concluded that there are human obstacles at M'sila University. It also agrees with the study of researchers Zainab Basu and Noura Mahboub (2013), who concluded that there are human obstacles that affect the performance of workers in the Oasis Mills-Tougourt. It also agreed with the results of the study by the researcher Al-Abed Hawari (2015), which concluded that there are human obstacles in the institutions of Adrar. We also find that the results of our study are inconsistent with the rest of the other studies.
- Analysis and Discussion of the Results of the Fourth Partial Hypothesis “There are financial obstacles that prevent the application of total quality management in the Directorate of Youth and Sports, Souk Ahras.” Through tables (30,31,32,33,34,35,36,37), it is clear to us that there are financial obstacles in the Directorate of Youth and Sports, Souk Ahras. Through this, the hypothesis related to the financial aspect is fulfilled. Our results agree with the study of Aqaq Khadija (2019), which concluded through our study that there are financial obstacles that prevent the application of total quality management at M'sila University. The results of our study also agree with the study of researcher Munir bin Muhammad Saeed bin Muhammad Qutb

(2008), who concluded that there are financial obstacles in the stages of public education in the Saudi capital, Jeddah. The results of our study also agree with the study of the researcher Al-Abed Hawari (2015), which concluded that there are financial obstacles that affect the performance of workers in the local administrations of Adrar. The results of our study are inconsistent with the rest of the other studies.

10- Conclusion

Total Quality Management is the most important modern management concept that helps institutions improve their performance and achieve excellence in the quality levels of their products. The application of ISO standards and obtaining a qualification certificate is considered a guide and guarantee for those dealing with these institutions. Total Quality Management is the most important competitive factor required in order to promote work within the Directorate of Youth and Sports.

We come to the following results :

- There are organizational obstacles at an acceptable level with a statistical significance that prevent the application of total quality management in the Directorate of Youth and Sports in Souk Ahras. Considering that changing the organizational culture for the implementation of total quality management is very difficult, and takes a long time, and the reason may be due to fear of change, this process needs a process of convincing the benefits of this new application in the organization, and more motivation for everyone to accommodate the transformation process.
- There are administrative obstacles at an acceptable level with a statistical significance that prevent the application of total quality management in the Directorate of Youth and Sports in the state of Souk Ahras. As the administration fails to implement it if the administrative work procedures do not support the implementation of this task, and therefore, the administration must clarify the possible benefits from its application as a basic work.
- There are human obstacles at an acceptable level with a statistical significance that prevent the application of total quality management in the Directorate of Youth and Sports in the state of Souk Ahras, as attention to the human factor has become one of the basics and to meet their needs and professional aspirations, and continuous training for them increases their efficiency, as it is a great priority in activating total quality management because achieving meaningful success requires devoting the necessary

attention and care to individuals, starting with the process of testing, appointment, performance evaluation, training and development programs, methods of motivation, and also striving to prove personal differences in work for the purpose of achieving continuous improvement in performance.

- There are financial obstacles at an acceptable level with a statistical significance that prevent the application of total quality management in the Directorate of Youth and Sports in the state of Souk Ahras. It is known that in order for any institution to succeed, it must provide huge sources of funding in order to be able to apply total quality management, especially for an institution such as the Directorate of Youth and Sports.

In the light of that, the researcher recommends the following:

-Spreading the philosophy and culture of total quality within the youth and sports directorates and creating the appropriate organizational climate for the success of its application.

-The Directorate of Youth and Sports must believe in teamwork.

-Holding training courses for the workers of the Directorate of Youth and Sports to introduce the mechanisms of applying total quality management.

-Reducing the centralization of administrative decision-making.

-Reconsidering the requirements of total quality management to implement strategic plans in light of work requirements.

-Providing all the financial and material capabilities in a sufficient and appropriate manner to achieve business objectives.

-Reliance on a financial system for total quality management characterized by transparency and responsibility in order to develop and employ the financial and human capabilities and energies.

-The Directorate of Youth and Sports should adopt modern information technology systems.

-This opens the door for the contributions of experienced and qualified people to offer their opinions, take decisions, and contribute to the adoption and spread of a culture of total quality management.

-Quality cells must be activated at the level of the structures of the Directorate of Youth and Sports. The workers of the Youth and Sports Directorate also contributed by giving a set of suggestions, including:

-These requirements must be activated with tighter control and to obtain an idea of the most important deviations that make it difficult to apply the philosophy of total quality management in the Directorate of Youth and Sports.

-It must focus on highly qualified human resource, which did not allow it to do so for various reasons.

-These requirements must be met, and there is a strong will on the part of the higher management to apply total quality management.

-The workers of the Directorate of Youth and Sports confirmed that there are available requirements that should be addressed in the service of total quality management.

-All requirements are available, and it is able to reduce obstacles while increasing interest in the subject only.

They also added the need to pay attention to spreading the culture of quality and increasing financial support in the application of total quality management.

-All of them have requirements that allow avoiding and overcoming obstacles of total quality management application with the need to adapt them according to the requirements of each directorate. The management of the directorate must activate the total quality system by establishing the necessary mechanisms.

This study may open future prospects, including:

-Our study was limited to the views of the Directorate of Youth and Sports workers. So, subsequent studies should focus on the opinions of other structures.

-Carrying out similar studies that address the obstacles to the total quality management application in the directorates of youth and sports, as it deals with different dimensions.

-Carrying out similar studies using tools and sources different from our study, as an example, the corresponding tool.

-The administration of the Directorate of Youth and Sports must activate the total quality system by developing the necessary mechanisms and trying to emulate global models of excellence in the directorates while working to spread a culture of quality to the directorate's categories of administrators and employees.

-attempting to persuade employees and administrators to pay attention and embrace the concept of total quality management for growth and innovation.

11- References :

1. Al-Ahmad Al-Thani, Faisal bin Jassim bin Mohammed. (2008). Total quality management for scientific institutions. Beirut: House of Knowledge.
2. Ibrahim, Marwan Abdel-Mojibed. (2004). Sports for All (1st Edition). Amman: House of Culture for Publishing and Distribution.
3. Al-Trabeka Mamoun, Mamoun Al-Shili, and others. (2001). Total Quality Management (1st ed.). Amman: Dar Al-Safaa for printing and publishing.
4. Raad Abdullah Al-Tai, and Aissa Qadad. (2008). Total Quality Management. Amman: Al-Yazuri House.
5. Abdel Wahab Al-Azzawi. (2002). Quality and environmental management systems. Amman: Wael Publishing House.
6. Omar Nasrallah. (2016). Scientific Research Methods and Its Applications (2nd ed.). Amman: Dar Wael for printing, publishing and distribution.
7. Omar Wasfi Aqili. (2001). The Complete Methodology of Total Quality Management (1st ed.). Amman: Wael Publishing House.
8. Mahfoud Ahmed Judeh. (2004). Total quality management concepts and applications. Amman: Wael Publishing House.
9. Mohamed Abu Tamer. (2003). Scientific Research Methodology, Rules, Stages, and Applications (2nd ed.). Amman: Dar Wael for printing and publishing.
10. Yusuf Hakim Al-Taie. (2009). Quality management systems in production and service organizations. Amman: Al-Yazuri Scientific Publishing and Distribution House.
11. Abdul Sattar Ali. (2008). The Applications in Total Quality Management. Amman: Dar El Masira.
12. Musa al-Lawzi. (2004). 27 to 29 November. Total Quality Management. Sharm El-Shaikh. Egypt: The Fifth Annual Arab Conference on Management.
13. Muhammad al-Eid Khashim. (2009). Total Quality Management and Enterprise Strategy – Sonelgaz Foundation – Master’s thesis, Faculty of Economics, Management and Commercial Sciences. M’sila: Mohamed Boudiaf University.